

Do Grassland Conservation Subsidies Influence Farm Efficiency? Evidence from a French Natural Experiment

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Abstract

In this paper, we investigate the impact of an exogenous source of income support variation related to Less Favored Areas (LFA) and the grassland premium (PHAE) on farms' technical efficiency (TE), environmental efficiency (EE) in France. We exploit the 2015 CAP reform, which serves as a natural experiment since it affects three groups of farms differently. We employ a combination of difference-in-differences and inverse propensity score weighting, comparing farms that benefited from an increase in LFA payments (*winners*) to farms that did not experience a change (*neutrals*). We also compared farms that suffered from the loss of the grassland premium (*losers*) to neutral farms. Our findings suggest that the variation in income support has led to a reduction in TE without significant effect on EE.

Keywords : Less Favored Area, Grassland Premium, Technical Efficiency, Environmental Efficiency, France.

JEL Codes : Q12, Q15, Q18, Q57, C31.

1 Introduction

Agriculture is widely recognized as delivering not only commodity outputs but also rural amenities and other functions (Randall, 2002). Indeed, there is a consensus that ecosystem services from the agricultural sector can be valuable, representing good environmental externalities (Aznar, 2023), and should be taken into account in public policy design. Among these services, grasslands are a prime example. They contribute to enhancing water quality (Hecht et al., 2016; Isselstein et al., 2014), conserving biodiversity (Chemini and Rizzoli, 2003), providing important landscape amenities (Bellarby et al., 2013), improving carbon sequestration (Soussana et al., 2010), and potentially increasing production (Bareille and Dupraz, 2020).

Grasslands have been facing decline and abandonment in many European countries (Peeters, 2009; Habel et al., 2013). The decrease in grassland can be attributed to two main reasons: the conversion of grassland into arable land and the abandonment of grassland that is unsuitable for cropping (Hecht et al., 2016). Therefore, European countries have introduced protection measures to prevent grassland abandonment (Santos et al., 2021; Peeters, 2009). Different types of actions such as Less Favored Areas (LFA) or grassland premium (PHAE) have been taken throughout the years in France.

In 2015, the CAP reform introduced a fixed component in LFA payments, resulting in an increase of 70 €. Simultaneously, the grassland premium (PHAE) was eliminated as it did not offer significant environmental benefits (Chabé-Ferret and Subervie, 2009; Desjeux et al., 2015). The fixed component newly introduced was meant to compensate for the PHAE loss, as many farmers were receiving both forms of income support (Gallic and Marcus, 2019). However, some farms were only receiving one of the two supports. As a result of the increase in LFA payments and the elimination of the PHAE, the reform affected different groups of farmers. There were primarily three distinct groups: those who lost the PHAE, those who experienced an increase in LFA payments, and those who lost the PHAE but also received an increase in LFA payments. The first type of farmer, who were only receiving the grassland premium (PHAE), will be labeled *losers* as the reform induced a significant loss of income for them. The second type of farmer, who had only LFA payments, will be called *winners* as their income support has been revalued. The third type of farmers will be the *neutrals* to highlight the fact that the loss of the PHAE was somehow compensated by the increase in the LFA payments.

Previous studies have examined the impact of LFA payments on different aspects of technical efficiency (TE) and grassland. For instance, Baráth et al. (2020) investigated the effect of investment subsidies, LFA payments, and agri-environmental subsidies (AES) on Total Factor Productivity (TFP), technical change (TCH), TE, and scale efficiency (SE). Using a difference-in-differences with matching method, their findings indicate that the LFA payments did not have a significant effect on TFP, TCH, TE, and SE in Slovenia between 2006 and 2013. Similarly, Latruffe and Desjeux (2016) studied the impact of rural development subsidies, such as agri-environmental payment (AEP) and LFA, on TE and productivity change in France. Their econometric fixed-effect model and ordinary least squares (OLS) model esti-

mations showed mixed results. While rural development subsidies did not have a significant effect on TE, they could have positive or negative impacts on its components depending on the type of farming. The authors suggested that LFA payments may have kept inefficient farms in the sector, although they may provide good land conditions in LFA areas. Some other studies, such as the one of [Zhu and Lansink \(2010\)](#), included LFA payments in decoupled subsidies, making it difficult to estimate their proper effect on TE. Meanwhile, [Desjeux et al. \(2015\)](#) demonstrated that LFA payments had a negative delayed impact on grassland index in Midi-Pyrénées, France.

Studies on the effectiveness of grassland premiums have yielded mixed results. According to [Chabé-Ferret and Subervie \(2009\)](#), grassland premiums have had a small but positive impact on permanent grassland in France. However, [Desjeux et al. \(2015\)](#) found that the grassland premium reduced the grassland index in France and Midi-Pyrénées between 2007 and 2010. [Gallic and Marcus \(2019\)](#) analyzed the impact of the 2015 CAP reform on grassland areas in France and found that the introduction of the LFA fixed part led to an increase in grassland area for winners and a decrease for losers due to the loss of the PHAE. Overall, the effectiveness and cost-effectiveness of grassland premiums remain uncertain. In this study, we are interested in the effect of the exogenous variation of income support (increase of LFA and loss of PHAE) on technical efficiency (TE), environmental efficiency (EE) and grassland share. We intend to use the 2015 LFA CAP reform as an exogenous source of variation in income support, i.e. a natural experiment. First, it will allow us to evaluate the effect of the fixed-part increase in the LFA payments by comparing *winners vs neutrals*. Second, we will also assess the impact PHAE lost on farmers by comparing *losers vs neutrals*.

Our work is also part of the recent literature that examines the influence of subsidies on the economic and environmental efficiency of farms. First, the theoretical results concerning the subsidy–efficiency relationship are inconclusive. On the one hand, subsidies may reduce farmers’ effort ([Martin and Page, 1983](#)) or alter their risk attitudes ([Serra et al., 2008a](#)), which could result in a decline in technical efficiency. In a broader sense, a wealth effect may elucidate the inverse relationship between subsidies and technical efficiency. The income stabilization afforded by subsidies may, in fact, distort the incentives for efficient production. Conversely, subsidies may facilitate the overcoming of financial constraints that impede efficient restructuring or modernisation, thereby increasing technical efficiency through investments in advanced technologies ([Blancard et al., 2006](#); [Zhu and Lansink, 2010](#)). It is similarly plausible that subsidies have no significant effect on technical efficiency, given that this is not their primary objective. The empirical evidence is also inconclusive indicating both significant positive and negative effects, as well as instances where subsidies have no significant impact on farm technical efficiency ([Serra et al., 2008b](#); [Kumbhakar and Lien, 2010](#); [Zhu and Lansink, 2010](#)). Furthermore, [Latruffe et al. \(2017\)](#) put forth an innovative SFA approach that considers the endogeneity of CAP subsidy levels. Their findings indicate that the relationship between CAP subsidies and agricultural output is either positive, neutral, or negative, depending on the country under examination. Additionally, they suggest that the relationship between subsidies and TE is weakened by the introduction of decoupled subsidies in 2003. Similarly, the literature focusing on the relationship between public support and envi-

ronmental efficiency (EE) is inconclusive. Some studies suggest a positive impact when subsidies is either decoupled or tied to environmental objectives (Lankoski and Thiem, 2020; Bernini and Galli, 2024). However, other studies find no significant relationship (Ait Sidhoum et al., 2023; Diop and Védrine, 2025) or even indicate a negative impact (Eder et al., 2021). This confirm the conclusion of a meta-analysis conducted by Minviel and Latruffe (2017) highlighting that the results from empirical studies differ not only in context (country, period, types of subsidies and types of farms) but also in data used (cross-sectional or panel data) and methodologies employed (e.g. parametric or non-parametric approaches). Consequently, it remains unclear whether the direction of the subsidy–efficiency relationship identified in the empirical literature is random or systematically related to the characteristics of the studies.

Our contribution to the literature is threefold. First, given that the theoretical results on this issue are ambiguous and the empirical results in the literature are inconclusive, our paper proposes to address this issue by exploiting the reform of the grassland conservation policy in France, which was an exogenous shock for a large proportion of farms. Second, to the best of our knowledge, this is also the first paper to assess the impact of PHAE and LFA on EE. Third, we observe both negative and positive shocks, which allows us to test whether the effect of a variation in subsidies is symmetric. Thus, to the best of our knowledge, this is also the first study to assess the impact of income loss on TE and EE in Europe. This issue is important for policy makers as it gives a clear idea of the knock-on effects of income loss for farmers and the potential impact of a lack of clear exit strategy. This is also more relevant in our case as the PHAE has been considered as an income support rather than an environmental one (Poux, 2015).

Our results show that a variation in grassland conservation subsidies affect negatively technical efficiency whatever the direction of the variation of the income support. The decrease in technical efficiency correspond to an average loss from 11,000 to 24,000 € per farm. The results do not show significant effect on Environmental Efficiency or Grassland Share of Used Agricultural Area. This set of results leads us to suggest that the economic consequences of this type of subsidy reform, whatever its direction, should be carefully considered, as it generates an asymmetric negative shock without improving environmental efficiency.

The structure of the paper is as follows: In the next section, we provide background information and a literature review. Section 3 presents our methodology and the computation of our outcomes. We describe our sample and sources of data in Section 4. The results of our estimations for both *winner*s and *loser*s are presented in Section 5, and Section 6 concludes the paper.

2 Background and Literature Review

2.1 Grassland Conservation Programs Reform Background in France

The 2015 CAP reform brought multiple changes both in the 1st and 2nd pillars. Some of the novelty of the reform is related to changes in the extensive grazing scheme (PHAE),

the upgrading of the compensatory allowance for areas facing natural constraints (LFA) and the creation of an agri-environmental and climatic measure "système herbager et pastoral" (AEMC SHP). These measures are part of the 2nd pillar which aims to promote rural development.

The PHAE was introduced in 2003 in France with the objectives of preserving grassland and extensive management of surfaces. It replaced the French Grassland Conservation Program, called "Prime au Maintien des Systemes d'Elevage Extensifs" (PMSEE) and created ten years before. Between 2003 and 2013, there were two main criteria to receive the PHAE: (i) a loading ratio¹ between 1.4 and 1.8 LU/ha before 2007 depending on the region, and between 0.35 and 1.4 LU/ha after 2007, (ii) specialization rate² between 50% and 75% before 2007 depending on the department, and higher than 75% after 2007. In 2015, the PHAE was eliminated because of its ambiguity between economic and environmental targets (Gallic and Marcus, 2019). Indeed, it was considered as a pure economic measure (Poux, 2015) with small environmental additionality (Chabé-Ferret and Voia, 2021).

The LFA payments are designed to help farmers located in recognized constraint areas. Indeed, it aimed to take into account the fact that additional cost and income loss inherent to constrained area could be detrimental for agriculture survival (European Union, 2013). Constrained areas are defined based concepts related to climatic and/or soil parameters (i.e. excessive soil moisture, poor chemical properties, drought or low temperatures) and physical parameters (i.e. steep slopes) (European Union, 2013). Moreover, the LFA payments target extensive breeding, as the loading rate should be between 0.2 and 2, and intend to preserve grassland as for the PHAE. Grasslands taken into account in the schemes are temporary grassland, permanent grassland, fodder and leguminous fodder, and payments can range from 90€/ha to 400€/ha depending on the constrained area (Hanus et al., 2017). Therefore, the LFA scheme has a broader accounting of the grassland compared to PHAE, which was only focused on permanent and temporary grassland. The LFA payments have been incorporated in the CAP since 1973 in France (Hanus et al., 2017) and 1975 in Europe (Takayama et al., 2021). The importance of the LFA scheme has been more recognized in 2014 as it was not only revalued by 15%, but was also renewed in the 2015 CAP reform (European Union, 2013) with an increase of 70 €. The Table 1 describes changes related to LFA after the 2015 reform.

A subsidy premium of 70 € was added as a fixed component due to the suppression of the PHAE, as most farms received both measures (Poux, 2015). In total, the LFA subsidies amount to 967 Million € in 2016 and 1,056 Million € in 2017, which makes it the most important part of the 2nd pillar in value. The payment ranges from 90 to 400 € according to the location.

Figure 1 present the average grassland premium and LFA payments from 2010 to 2018.

We can see the decline in PHAE from 2014 and the increase of the LFA from the same year, due to both the 10% revaluation and the increase in the fixed part. Taking into account all these elements, the reform has made substantial changes on farm subsidies. Some of them

¹density of livestock units (LU) per ha.

²sum of permanent and temporary grassland over the UAA.

Table 1: LFA payments Change following the reform

Criteria	Before 2015 CAP reform	After 2015 CAP reform
Farmers and farms' beneficiary Definition		
<i>Farming activity</i>	Not retired; commitment to continue activity for 5 years.	Criterion withdrew
<i>Age</i>	Eligible if under 65 years old	Criterion withdrew
<i>Location of farm residence</i>	Must be in disadvantage zone	No condition for farm residence
Locally dominant grassland systems targeting		
<i>Animal Production</i>	Minimum 3 grazing Lus (cows, goats, sheep) Decrease of LFA payment rate for low (0.1 LU/ha) and high animal density (2 LU/ha in mountains areas and 1.6 LU/ha in grassland).	LU pigs added to previous Lus. No longer LFA for very low stock density (0.1 LU/ha) or high density (2.3 LU/ha) in mountains areas
<i>Plant Production</i>	Only for dry mountains and certain types of production (medicinal plants)	All marketed areas and mountainous areas (without crops)
Payments		
<i>Maximum payment rate</i>	250 ha (could be higher for the first 25ha)	450/ha in mountainous areas
<i>Limit for subsidies areas</i>	50 ha fodder or cultivated area	50 ha cultivated or 75 ha fodder area

have lost a income support (PHAE). Even though they might adopt the AECM SHP, they might not be eligible. Other farms have seen an increase in their support such as the one receiving only the LFA payments. Another type of farm, receiving both the LFA payment and the PHAE before 2015, might benefit from compensation mechanism between the loss of the PHAE and the revaluation of LFA payments. In this case, they will not be affected. Therefore, the 2015 CAP reform came as an exogenous change that split farms between different groups. This gives us a natural experimental design that will be used to assess the causal effect on different outcome. The next section will present similar studies.

2.2 A Literature Review on the incidence of Grassland Conservation Programs in France

Grassland programs have been aiming to improve biodiversity and to prevent grassland reduction. Indeed, grassland areas have experienced reduction in Europe mainly due to the intensification and cropland activities (Peeters, 2009). Many European countries have set up measures that prevent the loss of grassland such as cross compliance rules of the CAP (Hecht et al., 2016). Indeed, grasslands are recognized by the bundle of ecosystem services that

Figure 1: Average yearly LFA payments (ICHN) and grassland premium (PHAE) in Euros.
Source: authors' own elaboration.

they provide (Schils et al., 2022): carbon sequestration (Soussana et al., 2010), hedge against flood or erosion (Macleod et al., 2013), or water purification and animal feed (Isselstein et al., 2014). Few studies have analyzed grassland programs in France.

Chabé-Ferret and Voia (2021) took advantage of an eligibility change in Grassland Program in France and evaluated its effects on grassland areas, cropland area and other indicators using a difference-in-differences approach. Indeed, the reform that came into force in 2000 relaxed constraint on specialization rate that allows some farms to be eligible for the first time. Therefore, they made a comparison between farms that all respected eligibility criteria (*always takers*) and the one that benefit from the eligibility change (*compliers*). Their results showed a small increase in the share of permanent grassland as well as the specialization rate, and a potential arbitrage between permanent grassland and cropland following the reform. The findings also highlighted low additionality from the program, which jeopardized its cost-effectiveness.

Chabé-Ferret and Subervie (2009) studied two grassland measures (AEM19 and AEM20) on the share of grassland and the UAA of farms. These two measures are part of the second pillar of CAP which is focused on rural development. Even though their results suggested small increase in either or both outcomes depending on the measure, they concluded that the results might not be robust. Indeed, the existence of time-varying unobserved characteristics might compromise the results.

These low effects of grassland programs, especially when they designed as agri-environmental measures (AEM or AECM) could be related to adoption problems. Indeed, Carvin

and Saïd (2020) showed that there are few adopters of AECM with greater impact because farms prefer measures to maintain their practices rather than changing them radically.

Desjeux et al. (2015) evaluated the effect of rural development measures, such as LFA area payments and grassland premium, on nature value indicators. Their results showed that grassland premium has reduced grassland index from 2007 to 2013. Moreover, they also found a negative and significant effect for Midi-Pyrénées region of the LFA payments (LFA payments). Their results are justified by the fact that grassland premium did not prevent conversion from permanent grassland to temporary grassland and then beneficiaries farms have more likely carried out such conversion.

More recently, Gallic and Marcus (2019) have also used the 2015 CAP reform as a natural experiment to evaluate the effect of the loss of the PHAE but also the increase of the LFA payments in France. They found a reduction of 2.2 percentage points of the share of the grass area for farmers who lost the PHAE and an increase of 3.3 of the shares of the grass area for farmers who have experienced an increase in the LFA payment.

In this study, we are interested in the 2015 CAP reform on farm technical and environmental efficiency. Since the effect of this reform on land-use are studied by Gallic and Marcus (2019), our work differs in several ways. First, we focus on the incidence of the reform on productivity outcomes. The productivity outcomes are here technical, meaning the ability of farms to obtain production from inputs at hand, and environmental, *i.e.* the capacity to reduce environmental detrimental inputs without degrading the level of production or the economic value added. Second, we propose an alternative econometric strategy, a DID weighting strategy instead of two-way fixed effects, to address the recent literature highlighting the limitations of two-way fixed effects in a causal inference framework (Imai and Kim, 2019).

2.3 Possible Transmission Channels between Income Support Change and Efficiency Indicators

Following the 2015 CAP reform, *winner*s and *loser*s' productivity can be affected in many ways. *Winner*s might maintain or increase their extensive grassland. This might be at the cost of cropland (Chabé-Ferret and Voia, 2021). This behavior might entail potential environmental efficiency gain as grassland, especially permanent grassland, can be substitute to fertilizer and pesticides (Bareille and Dupraz, 2020). However technical efficiency's effect remains unclear. On the one hand, Bareille and Dupraz (2020) showed that permanent grassland can have a positive effect of production if the crop diversity is low. In this case, maintaining or increasing permanent grassland could potentially have a positive impact on technical efficiency as the level of production could be increased or the reliance on some (detrimental) inputs could be reduced. On the other hand, if the maintenance or the increase in grassland is made at the expenses of cropland (Chabé-Ferret and Voia, 2021), farms might face a reduction in production, which might influence the technical efficiency negatively. Moreover, the technical efficiency-subsidy literature provides an overall negative effect of subsidies in most cases (Minviel and Latruffe, 2017). Indeed, subsidies might distort farm behaviors by reducing their managerial effort (Martin and Page, 1983) or smoothing

production risks (Serra et al., 2008b; Hennessy, 1998) in such a way they will not adopt efficient production strategy. Therefore, with more subsidies without additional requirements, farmers might be less motivated to do more (Zhu and Lansink, 2010). Hence, we hypothesize that winner will face a technical efficiency reduction following the introduction of the fixed part of the LFA.

After the 2015 CAP reform, *losers* may have reduced their extensive grassland due to the loss of financial incentives. This reduction might lead to an increase in the use of pesticides or fertilizers, which could have a negative impact on environmental efficiency. As a result, we anticipate a negative effect of the 2015 reform on environmental efficiency for the *losers*. If grassland is converted into cropland, we might anticipate an increase in production if crop diversification is well-established. However, if grassland is abandoned because it is not suitable for crops, the effect on production and productivity may be positive or neutral. The empirical results of this study will shed light on these issues. The next section outlines the econometric approach employed.

3 Econometric Strategy

3.1 Efficiency Estimates

In this section, we will outline the methods used to calculate two key indicators: technical efficiency (TE) and environmental efficiency (EE). These indicators are essential for evaluating the performance of farms and identifying areas for improvement. The other outcome are explained in Table C1. TE and EE are computed using the two main streams in the efficiency literature: Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA) which is a parametric method (Aigner et al., 1977), and Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) which is a non-parametric method (Charnes et al., 1978).

Technical efficiency and environmental efficiency are first computed with the methodology developed by Reinhard et al. (1999). It is a parametric modelisation, therefore related to SFA, based on a production function (Battese, 1992). The production function links the output produced and the inputs which were used. It can be written as follows :

$$Y_{it} = f(X_{it}; Z_{it}; \beta) \cdot \exp\{V_{it} - U_i\}. \quad (1)$$

Christensen et al. (1973) offers a function form specification of the Equation 1 that can be written as :

$$\begin{aligned}
\ln Y_{it} = & \beta_0 \\
& + \sum_{j=1}^n \beta_j \ln X_{kit} + \beta_z \ln Z_{it} \\
& + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n \beta_{jk} \ln X_{ijt} * \ln X_{ijk} \\
& + \sum_{j=1}^n \beta_{jz} \ln X_{ijt} * \ln Z_{it} \\
& + \frac{1}{2} \beta_{zz} (\ln Z_{it})^2 \\
& + \beta_t T + \frac{1}{2} \beta_{tt} T^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{it} T * \ln X_{it} + \beta_{it} T * \ln Z_{it} \\
& + \beta_l L + \frac{1}{2} \beta_{ll} L^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{il} L * \ln X_{il} + \beta_{il} L * \ln Z_{il} \\
& + \beta_l N + \frac{1}{2} \beta_{ll} N^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{il} N * \ln X_{il} + \beta_{il} N * \ln Z_{il} \\
& + V_{it} - U_i
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where

- Y_{it} is the output (gross production)³ of farm i at time t ;
- X_{it} is the conventional inputs vector, and n the inputs total. Inputs considered here are: utilized agricultural area (UAA), fixed assets, intermediary consumption (without energy, Fertilizer and crop protection expenses) and agricultural working unit (AWU)⁴
- Z_{it} is a undesirable input. It is the sum of expenses in fertilizers, crop protection and energy consumption (electricity, gas, etc);
- β is a vector of parameters;
- V_{it} is the random error terms measuring the effects of statistical noise and is assumed to be independently and identically distributed (i.i.d) of $N(0, \sigma_v^2)$ distribution;
- U_i is the non-negative random error term which measures the inefficiency. It is assumed to be i.i.d. of $N^+(\mu, \sigma_v^2)$;
- T are time dummies that account for technological change over year,

³The total includes the basic gross production from animals, animal products, crops, crop products, horticultural products, as well as outputs from immobilized production, contract services, the sale of by-products, animal boarding, land rented for sowing, other leasing activities, agritourism, and secondary activities. The output variable is inflation-adjusted using agricultural product price indices (base year 2010), sourced from the National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies (INSEE). Specific indices are applied to each input to account for inflation. Additionally, the output excludes subsidies.

⁴1 AWU = 1600 hours.

- N is a categorical variable that account for the fact that farm is whether a *winner*, a *loser* or a *neural*, and
- L equals 1 if farm is in a less favored area (LFA). This is included to account for the fact that there are difference in production technologies between farms in LFA and those not located in LFA. TE could be bias if we don not take into account these differences (Baráth et al., 2018).

For technical efficient farms, $U_{it} = 0$ in Equation 2, which means that there is no deviation of frontier related to inefficiency. The environmental efficiency (EE) can be derived from Equation 2 with $U_{it} = 0$. EE is defined as the ratio between the minimum feasible quantity of the undesirable input, i.e. Z_{it}^F , and the actual quantity used by the farm Z_{it} ($EE = Z_{it}^F / Z_{it}$) (Reinhard et al., 1999). Therefore, EE is the capacity of the farm to use the minimum of the undesirable input while maintaining the same level of output. It is therefore an non radial measure (Reinhard et al., 1999), meaning that it is a non-radial measure of farm efficiency in the undesirable input use. The logarithm of an environmental efficient producer is obtained by replacing $U_i = 0$ and $Z_{it} = Z_{it}^F$ with Z_{it}^F in Equation 2, with Z_{it}^F the minimal feasible undesirable input:

$$\begin{aligned}
\ln Y_{it} &= \beta_0 \\
&+ \sum_{j=1}^n \beta_j \ln X_{kit} + \beta_z \ln Z_{it}^F \\
&+ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^n \sum_{k=1}^n \beta_{jk} \ln X_{ijt} * \ln X_{ijk} \\
&+ \sum_{j=1}^n \beta_{jz} \ln X_{ijt} * \ln Z_{it}^F \\
&+ \frac{1}{2} \beta_{zz} (\ln Z_{it}^F)^2 \\
&+ \beta_t T + \frac{1}{2} \beta_{tt} T^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{it} T * \ln X_{it} + \beta_{it} T * \ln Z_{it} \\
&+ \beta_l L + \frac{1}{2} \beta_{ll} L^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{il} L * \ln X_{il} + \beta_{il} L * \ln Z_{il} \\
&+ \beta_l N + \frac{1}{2} \beta_{ll} N^2 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{il} N * \ln X_{il} + \beta_{il} N * \ln Z_{il} \\
&+ V_{it}
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

The EE is obtained by setting equations (2) = (3):

$$\frac{1}{2} \beta_{zz} (\ln Z_{it}^F - \ln Z_{it})^2 + (\ln Z_{it}^F - \ln Z_{it}) \left[\beta_z + \sum_{j=1}^m \beta_{jz} \ln X_{ij,t} + \beta_{zz} \ln Z_{i,t} \right] + U_{i,t} = 0 \tag{4}$$

with $\ln EE = \ln Z_{it}^F - \ln Z_{it}$.

EE final expression is derived from the resolution of Equation 4:

$$\ln EE_{i,t} = \left[- \left(\beta_z + \sum_{j=1}^m \beta_{jz} \ln X_{ij,t} + \beta_{zz} \ln Z_{i,t} \right) \pm \left\{ \left(\beta_z + \sum_{j=1}^m \beta_{jz} \ln X_{ij,t} + \beta_{zz} \ln Z_{i,t} \right)^2 - 2\beta_{zz} U_{i,t} \right\}^{0.5} \right] \beta_{zz}. \quad (5)$$

Basically, the TE is estimated econometrically and the EE is derived from Equation 4 thanks to estimated parameters (β_z and β_{zz}) and the inefficiency term U_{it} (Reinhard et al., 1999; Marchand and Guo, 2014; Diop and Védrine, 2025). It is worth noting that instead of using bad outputs as detrimental input similar to Reinhard et al. (1999), an environmentally detrimental inputs is preferred here as it aligns better with Reinhard et al. (1999)'s definition of environmental efficiency (Diop and Védrine, 2025). This can help solve the issues of the treatment of bad output as input (Färe and Grosskopf, 2003; Førsund, 2008).

However, one limitation of stochastic frontier analysis (SFA) methods is that they assume a known relationship between the variables under consideration. In cases where this relationship is unknown, the model may suffer from misspecification errors. To address this issue, we can complement SFA with data envelopment analysis (DEA), which does not require any prior assumptions about the functional form of the production function. By using both methods, we can better assess the robustness of the efficiency scores computed.

Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) can be defined as a data-oriented approach used to assess the performance of Decision-Making Units (DMUs), which can produce one or multiple outputs based on multiple inputs (Cooper et al., 2011). Here, there is no parametric specification imposed. Rather, the idea is to construct a frontier thanks to linear programming, and efficiency is measured based on the distance to that frontier. Observations which are on the frontier are considered as efficient and have a score of one. The one below are considered as non-efficient and their scores are lower than one.

DEA models have tried to incorporate environmental considerations in different ways: with undesirable output (Färe et al., 1989; Hailu and Veeman, 2001), with both undesirable inputs and output modeled with two technologies (Murty et al., 2012), or with link between environmental damage and economic outcomes (Kuosmanen and Kortelainen, 2005; Ait Sidhoum et al., 2022). We will use the "eco-efficiency model" as our primary modeling approach. This approach, also used in Ait Sidhoum et al. (2022), is particularly suited to our analysis as we do not have an undesirable output to account for. Eco-efficiency (thereafter Eco-Ef) can be define as the ability to produce the desired output with minimal environmental degradation (Kuosmanen and Kortelainen, 2005). It can be expressed as the ratio of economic value added (v^i) to environmental damage ($Z(p_n^i)$) (Kuosmanen and Kortelainen, 2005; Picazo-Tadeo et al., 2011; Ait Sidhoum et al., 2022) :

$$\text{Eco - ef}^i = \frac{v^i}{Z(p_n^i)} \quad (6)$$

$Z(\cdot)$ serves as a damage function which aggregate environmental damage to give an environmental damage score, *i.e.* $Z(p_n^i) = \sum_{n=1}^N w_n^i p_n^i$. w_n^i represents the weight associated the environmental pressure n for farm i . Therefore, $Z(p_n^i)$ is a weighted sum of environmental pressures (Kuosmanen and Kortelainen, 2005). However, determining the appropri-

ate weight for each pressure can be a challenge. One solution is to use data envelopment analysis (DEA) to obtain non-subjective weights that maximize the efficiency scores of farms compared to similar groups. This approach has been applied successfully in previous studies (Kuosmanen and Kortelainen, 2005) and can help ensure that the weights used to aggregate environmental pressures are appropriate and unbiased. The dual representation of the model can be expressed as follows (Picazo-Tadeo et al., 2011; Ait Sidhoum et al., 2022):

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min_{\theta^{i'}, \lambda^i} \{ \text{Eco} - \text{ef}^i \} = \theta^{i'} \\
& \text{s.t.} \\
& v^{i'} \leq \sum_{i=1}^I \lambda^i v^i \\
& \theta^{i'} p_n^{i'} \geq \sum_{i=1}^I \lambda^i p_n^i, n = 1, \dots, N \\
& \lambda^i \geq 0, i = 1, \dots, I
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where λ^i is the intensity variable that weights farms, θ^i is the radial efficiency score that measure the distance between the frontier and a specific farms. $\theta^i = 1$ implies that farms is eco-efficient, meaning a reduction of the environmental pressure could not be achieved without altering the economic value. $\theta^i < 1$ indicates that farm can achieve an equiproportional reduction of environmental damages with the same level of economic performance.

According to Ali and Seiford (1993), Picazo-Tadeo et al. (2011) and Ait Sidhoum et al. (2022), Equation 7 suffers from a weakness, as a farm could be efficient, i.e. $\theta^i = 1$, but still be able to reduce environmental pressures without any degradation of economic value added. This notion is related to Pareto-Koopmans efficiency, which implies that the farm is efficient if and only if any improvement of its inputs or output came at the cost of others inputs or output (Koopmans, 1951; Maleki et al., 2019). One way to overcome the problem is to use DEA model accounting for "slacks" (Charnes et al., 1985). Charnes et al. (1985) suggest that non-optimal farm can rendered Pareto-Koopmans efficient by accounting for excess in inputs (excess that still can be reduced to be Pareto-Koopmans efficient) and deficit in output. The model accounting for these slacks can be formulated as in Ali and Seiford (1993) and Picazo-Tadeo et al. (2011):

$$\begin{aligned}
& \max_{s_v^{i'}, s_p^{i'}, \lambda^i} \{ S^{i'} \} = s_v^{i'} + \sum_{n=1}^N s_{p,n}^{i'} \\
& \text{s.t.} \\
& v^{i'} + s_v^{i'} = \sum_{i=1}^I \lambda^i v^i \\
& \theta^{i'} p_n^{i'} - s_{p,n}^{i'} = \sum_{i=1}^I \lambda^i p_n^i, n = 1, \dots, N \\
& s_v^{i'}, s_{p,n}^{i'} \geq 0, n = 1, \dots, N \\
& \lambda^i \geq 0, i = 1, \dots, I
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

where s_p represents excess in environmental pressures and s_v is the deficit in economic value added. Equation 8 aims to maximize the sum of excess and deficit (s_p and s_v) by holding constant eco-efficiency score computed in Equation 7 (Picazo-Tadeo et al., 2011; Ait Sidhoum et al., 2022). Pressure excess (s_p) are combined with potential reduction of environmental pressure to assess pressure-specific eco-efficiency (specific to each of environmental pressure n). Torgersen et al. (1996) developed efficiency measures accounting for slacks that can be used in this paper. The idea is to determine pressure-specific eco-efficiency. The first step is to compute the aggregate reduction of pressure to be Pareto-Koopmans efficient:

$$R_n^i = (1 - \theta^{*i}) p_n^{i'} + s_{p,n}^{i'} \quad (9)$$

where $(1 - \theta^{*i}) p_n^{i'}$ is the proportional reduction in damage n and $s_{p,n}^{i'}$ accounts for excess-specific in damage n . Second, we compute the Pareto-specific level of damage in Equation 10.

$$\begin{aligned} R_{n,\text{Pareto-Koopmans}}^i &= p_n^{i'} - \left[(1 - \theta^{*i}) p_n^{i'} + s_{p,n}^{i'} \right] \\ &= \theta^{*i} p_n^{i'} - s_{p,n}^{i'} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

With Equation 9 and Equation 10, the damage specific eco-efficiency measure can be obtained the ratio of specific eco-efficient level of a pressure and its actual observed level (Picazo-Tadeo et al., 2011):

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Damage specific eco - efficiency}^i &= \frac{R_{n,\text{Pareto-Koopmans}}^i}{p_n^{i'}} \\ &= \theta^{*i} - \frac{s_{p,n}^{i'}}{p_n^{i'}} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Damage specific eco-efficiency are interpreted as the total proportional reduction of the damage to reach Pareto-Koopmans efficient frontier (Picazo-Tadeo et al., 2011; Ait Sidhoum et al., 2022). Figure A1 to ?? show the distribution of the density of all efficiency indicators. The next section presents our identification strategy.

3.2 Identification Strategy

The 2015 CAP reform resulted in the elimination of the PHAE in France. Concurrently, a new agri-environmental and climate measure, "système herbager et pastoral" (AECM-pasture), was introduced as a replacement option for farms that lost the PHAE. Most farms had been receiving both PHAE and LFA payments simultaneously (Hanus et al., 2017). As a result, it was decided to increase the LFA payment by a fixed amount of 70€. This change led to the separation of farms into three distinct groups. The first group consisted of farms that received both measures before the reform, and the added LFA payment was intended to compensate for the loss of the PHAE. We refer to these farms as *neutral* to emphasize the compensation mechanism between different measures. The second group of farms re-

ceived only the PHAE in 2013 and did not adopt any other measures (such as AECM-pasture) and therefore suffered from the loss of subsidies. We refer to these farms as *losers*. The third group of farms consisted of beneficiaries of LFA payments in 2013, who received an increased fixed payment from 2015 onwards. These farms are referred to as *winners*. It is worth noting that there may be a fourth group of new beneficiaries of LFA payments due to more relaxed requirements, as shown in [Table 1](#). However, we do not include these farms in our sample, although they could be an interesting case study. The reform provides an exogenous variation that allows us to categorize farms into three groups as aforementioned, creating a natural experiment setting. This enables us to draw causal inferences under certain conditions ([Meyer, 1995](#); [Dominici et al., 2014](#)). To compare the treatment effects, we employ the difference-in-differences (DID) methodology. The DID methodology involves subtracting the average change over time of non-treated farms (*neutrals*) from the average change over time of treated farms (i.e., *winners* and *losers*) ([Imbens and Wooldridge, 2009](#)). This approach removes both selection bias, which might result from systematic differences between treated and non-treated, and time-trend related bias, which could be related to events unrelated to the treatment ([Imbens and Wooldridge, 2009](#)). Thus, the DID methodology provides a robust estimation of the causal effects of the LFA scheme's fixed part and the PHAE loss on farms.

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta T_i + \theta t_{2015} + \gamma T_i \times t_{2015} + \varepsilon_{it}, \quad (12)$$

with Y_{it} , the outcome of interest, T_i is the treatment status (neutral, winner or losers), t_{2015} is the dummy variable for period after 2015 and γ is the parameter of interest that gives the effect of the income support variation.

One of the key assumptions for a valid DID is the parallel trend assumption. This assumption implies that, in the absence of the reform, the average change over time in outcomes for treated and non-treated would be equivalent. This assumption can be tested by running [Equation 12](#) before the reform. Results are presented in [Table C3](#). We can see that for the TE, the EE and the grassland rate, there is no evidence of violation of parallel trend assumptions. However, for other indicators we can see some significant difference especially for 2011 and 2012. From 2013, we might reasonably reject the violation of the parallel trend assumption. [Figure B7](#) To [Figure B8](#) give visual illustration of the parallel trend of our main estimators.

Another important hypothesis for the DID, from [Rubin \(1978\)](#), is the Stable Unit Treatment Value Assumption (SUTVA). It implies that the potential outcomes of each farm are only related to its treatment status, not the treatment status of other farms ([Angrist et al., 1996](#); [Imbens and Wooldridge, 2009](#)). [Gallic and Marcus \(2019\)](#) showed that the SUTVA was likely to be respected for the specialization rate since it is difficult to imagine a transfer of grassland between treated and non-treated farms. The same logic could be applied to the loading rate and the grassland rate in our case. Regarding our SFA and DEA indicators, we made the assumption, following [Chabé-Ferret and Subervie \(2013\)](#), that the prices of inputs and outputs and the determinants of input use (observed and unobserved) are not influ-

enced by the reform. Indeed, farms can be considered as price takers (Bernard and Prieur, 2007; De Wolf et al., 2007; Fradj et al., 2016) as input and output prices are set in the world market (Chabé-Ferret and Subervie, 2013). Moreover, as shown by Piot-Lepetit et al. (1997), the inputs in the agricultural sector are fixed or quasi-fixed and tend to adjust slowly to markets. Furthermore, in our estimation strategy of TE and EE via SFA, we took into account whether farms are *neutral*, *winners*, or *losers*.

However, selection needs to be completely random in DID. In our case, this assumption is not met as shown by Gallic and Marcus (2019). Observable differences might exist between *winners* and *neutral*, but also between *losers* and *neutral*. Characteristics such as organic farming, information bias, location, or having a specific label can induce differences between treated and control groups, leading to selection bias. To further address selection bias, we adopt a matching procedure, namely the Propensity Score Matching (PSM). The matching technique has been intensively used to assess causal effects (Caliendo and Kopeinig, 2008). Matching can be defined as any method that aims to balance the distribution of covariates in the treated and control groups' (Stuart, 2010). The idea is to construct a valid counterfactual group that can be compared to the treatment group based on the value of covariates X . This is achieved by defining a balancing score $b(x)$, *i.e.*, a function of observed covariates that allows treated and control observations to have the same conditional distribution of covariates given $b(x)$ (Rosenbaum and Rubin, 1983).

Following Rosenbaum and Rubin (1983), the balance score chosen here is the propensity score. Combining PSM with DID have been done largely in agricultural economics (Pufahl and Weiss, 2009; Chabé-Ferret and Subervie, 2013; Mennig and Sauer, 2020; Ait Sidhoum et al., 2022). Propensity score, noted $e(x)$, can be defined as the probability to be treated given the covariates at hand (Stuart, 2010). It can be expressed as follows (Imbens, 2004):

$$e(x) \equiv \Pr(T = 1 | X = x) = \mathbb{E}[W | X = x], \quad (13)$$

with T the treatment assignment. The propensity score, $e(x)$, groups all relevant covariates into one scalar (Stuart, 2010). To account for high dimensionality (Stuart, 2010; Caliendo and Kopeinig, 2008) or misspecification problems in the propensity score computation (Smith and Todd, 2005), we adopt the covariate balancing propensity score (CBPS) approach proposed by Imai and Ratkovic (2014). This approach simultaneously models treatment assignment and optimizes covariate balance, which is an advantage over the usual approach of estimating treatment assignment and checking the balance of covariates, which can lead to different specifications and treatment effect estimates.

Once we obtain the propensity score through the CBPS procedure, we can use it to derive weights for the treatment and control groups in our difference-in-differences (DID) regression analysis in Equation 12. Specifically, treatment observations will receive a weight of 1, and control observations will receive a weight of $e/(1 - e)$, where e is the propensity score. Weighting control observations with the propensity score ensures fully efficient estimation, as shown by Hirano et al. (2003).

All the covariates used in this study were collected in 2010 and capture various char-

acteristics of farmers and their farms. These include demographic variables such as age, experience, and education level, as well as farm-specific variables namely the adoption of an agri-environmental scheme, organic farming status, and receipt of a young farmer allowance. We also included variables related to product labeling (AOC, Label Rouge), as well as indicators of production intensity such as the loading rate, and the location of farms in areas with specific constraints. Our choice of covariates was informed by previous studies such as [Gallic and Marcus \(2019\)](#) and [Chabé-Ferret and Subervie \(2009\)](#).

An important step in the matching procedure is to assess the balance of covariates after matching. One way to do this is by using the standardized difference in means (B), which is a numerical diagnostic for the balance of covariates ([Rubin, 2001](#); [Stuart, 2010](#)). The B statistic is calculated as the difference in means between treatment and control groups for each covariate, divided by the standard deviation in the treatment group:

$$B = \frac{\bar{X}_t - \bar{X}_c}{\delta_t}. \quad (14)$$

The rule of thumb for the B statistic is that it should be close to 0, but a deviation of up to 0.25 is considered acceptable ([Stuart, 2010](#); [Imbens and Wooldridge, 2009](#)). Next, we present the data used in this study.

4 Data

Our study is based on a sample of commercial farms in France, drawn from the French FADN survey⁵. This survey is conducted by the French Ministry and covers over 7,000 farms annually, collecting data related to business and income activities. We use data from the period 2011-2016 for our study.

In addition to the French FADN data, we also utilize data from the European Rural Development Regulation second (RDR2) and third program (RDR3). These programs cover the period from 2007 to 2020 and provide information on subsidies related to grassland Payments and Agri-Environmental and climatic Measures (AECMs). The data is merged using the SIRET (Système d'Identification du Répertoire des Etablissements) identification number and the PACAGE identification number of farmers who receive CAP payments.

To extract pre-treatment covariates used for the CBPS procedure, we rely on the Agricultural Census of 2010 (AC-2010). The AC-2010 provides detailed information on socio-demographic and economic characteristics of farms, such as age, sex, labels, and AES. The French FADN and AC-2010 data are merged using the SIRET identification number. The final sample comprises 5,643 farms from 2011 to 2016. Descriptive statistics for the main indicators of the entire sample are presented in [Table 2](#), while [Table C2](#) provides information on the main variables for each group (*winners*, *neutrals* and *losers*).

Farms in the sample tend to be large, with the mean UAA reaching nearly 122 ha. The amount of LFA and grassland payments (up to 2015) received averages respectively 9540 € and 4525 €. The technical efficiency ranges from 0.587 to 0.691 depending on whether it was calculated with SFA or DEA. It means that farms can proportionally use 0.413 (0.309) of their

⁵Access to all data is given by the [CASD \(Centre d'Accès Sécurisé aux Données\)](#), Ref. 10.34724/CASD.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics on main variables and indicators from 2011 to 2016

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
UAA	5,643	121.684	80.835	7.41	975.56
LFA	5,643	9,540.987	8,318.949	0	91,812.461
PHAE	2,988	4,525.26	3,210.301	0	24,575
Technical Efficiency	5,643	0.691	0.158	0.118	0.987
Environmental Efficiency	5,642	0.412	0.237	0.001	0.984
Specialization Rate (%)	5,643	81.737	21.917	0	100
Grassland Rate	5,643	0.473	0.328	0	1
Loading Rate	5,643	1.097	1.026	0	25.562
Technical Efficiency (DEA)	5,643	0.587	0.205	0.03	1
Eco-efficiency	5,643	0.242	0.222	0	1

input while maintaining their level of production. The average eco-efficiency score reaches 0.24, indicating a large possible reduction of environmental damage without compromising economic added value. Eco-specific efficiency is lower than the global eco-efficiency score, which is normal as, by definition, these specific estimates will be lower than the general one (Picazo-Tadeo et al., 2011; Ait Sidhoum et al., 2022). The three groups represent respectively 162 for *losers*, 2,826 for *neutrals*, and 2,655 for *winners*. The next section presents the results of our estimations.

5 Results

This section presents results of covariates balancing, the effect of the increase in the LFA payments as well as the influence of the loss of the PHAE.

5.1 Balance of covariates

The balancing of covariates has been made for each comparison, namely winners vs. neutrals and losers vs. neutrals. Results can be seen Table 3 for former comparison, and in Table 4 for for the latter.

We can see that the balance of covariates after the matching is satisfying. The CBPS reduce drastically the standardized difference between treatment and control group with value close to 0. Therefore, the matching performed reduce considerably the difference between treated and non-treated units.

5.2 How Does the increase in the LFA payment influence TE and EE?

The results of the comparison between winners and neutrals are presented in Table 5. Our findings indicate a decrease in the grassland rate due to the added part of the LFA payments, although the result is not statistically significant. The reduction observed is of a very small magnitude, only 0.2 percentage points. This result goes against the findings of Gallic and Marcus (2019), but is consistent with the results of Desjeux et al. (2015) for Midi-Pyrénées (France). One possible explanation for this unexpected result is that the LFA payments incentivize the conversion of grassland into cropland. Since area under cereals for

Table 3: Covariates balance between *winners* and *neutrals*

Covariates	Before Matching		After Matching	
	Difference	Standardized difference	Difference	Standardized difference
Household head (HH) age	1.465	0.190	6.46e-07	7.44e-08
HH age squared	124.372	0.190	3.09e-05	4.27e-08
HH experience	1.589	0.193	-6.12e-08	-6.75e-09
Inheritance if HH is born before 1961	-0.248	-0.068	-2.38e-07	-6.60e-08
HH primary education (ref)	0	0.	0	.
HH secondary education	-0.025	-0.060	-2.95e-08	-8.34e-08
0 if HH sex is male	0	0.	0	.
1 if HH sex is female	0.006	0.021	1.70e-08	7.04e-08
Number of shareholders	-0.005	-0.006	-2.51e-07	-2.30e-07
1 if farm adopt an AES	-0.726	-1.522	0	.
1 if farm is organic	0.004	0.043	-1.48e-07	-7.78e-07
1 if farm received a young allowance	-0.056	-0.165	-5.90e-08	-1.78e-07
Majority of farm is not in a LFA (ref)	0	.	0	.
Majority of farm located in high mountains	-0.019	-0.146	6.44e-08	5.79e-07
Majority of farm located in mountains	-0.159	-0.319	1.71e-09	3.42e-09
Majority of farm located in piemont	-0.066	-0.219	-1.17e-08	-4.82e-08
Majority of farm located other LFA	0.237	0.485	0	.
1 if farms has quality sign (outside of wine)	-0.083	-0.168	4.83e-09	9.69e-09
1 if farm has AOC label	0.116	0.307	-5.30e-09	-1.54e-08
1 if farm has label rouge	0.019	0.050	2.03e-08	5.49e-08
Loading rate	0.156	0.130	-6.84e-08	-1.01e-07

Table 4: Covariates balance between *losers* and *neutrals*

Covariates	Before Matching		After Matching	
	Difference	Standardized difference	Difference	Standardized difference
Household head (HH) age	3.494	0.448	5.57e-06	1.57e-06
HH age squared	296.766	0.451	5.28e-04	1.49e-06
HH experience	2.560	0.312	6.42e-06	8.69e-07
Inheritance if HH is born before 1961	-1.183	-0.321	-4.49e-06	-1.13e-06
HH primary education (ref)	0	.	0	.
HH secondary education	0.101	0.237	2.91e-07	5.93e-07
0 if HH sex is male	0.090	0.330	2.58e-07	6.46e-07
1 if HH sex is female	-0.214	-0.276	1.09e-07	2.59e-07
Number of shareholders	0	0.	0	.
1 if farm adopt an AES	0.049	0.520	0	.
1 if farm is organic	0	0.	0	.
1 if farm received a young allowance	-0.173	-0.542	-2.13e-07	-5.32e-07
Majority of farm is not in a LFA (ref)	0	0.	0	.
Majority of farm located in high mountains	-0.025	-0.166	0	.
Majority of farm located in mountains	-0.567	-1.137	0	.
Majority of farm located in piemont	-0.131	-0.397	0	.
Majority of farm located other LFA	.001	0.001	0	.
1 if farms has quality sign (outside of wine)	-0.256	-0.517	-1.61e-07	-3.29e-07
1 if farm has AOC label	.174	0.419	0	.
1 if farm has label rouge	.142	0.362	4.57e-07	1.14e-06
Loading rate	.218	0.283	-4.64e-08	-1.54e-07

self-consumption are eligible for LFA payments but not for the PHAE, *winners* might have opted to increase their area under cereals for self-consumption at the expense of grassland, as suggested by Gallic and Marcus (2019). Furthermore, Desjeux et al. (2015) found that crop diversity increased in areas that received LFA payments, which might also be the case in our study. In addition, Allaire et al. (2018) found that the environmental impact of LFA and PHAE payments is less significant in areas facing specific challenges related to environmental management, such as those associated with agricultural intensification or trade-offs between grass and crop production.

The results also show a reduction in TE. The effect is even significant if we consider TE

Table 5: Comparison between *winner* and *neutral*

	Technical Efficiency		Environmental Efficiency	
	SFA	DEA	SFA	Eco-Efficiency
Average effect on treated	-0.001	-0.035***	-0.007	-0.003
Standard error	(0.002)	(0.013)	(0.006)	(0.016)
	Specialization rate	Grassland rate	Loading rate	
Average effect on treated	-0.505	-0.020	-0.021	
Standard error	(0.687)	(0.016)	(0.058)	
Number of observations	3546	3546	3546	3546

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * $p < 0.10$ ** $p < 0.05$ *** $p < 0.01$. The estimations are made on a balanced panel. Propensity score is used as weight for the ATT.

computed via DEA, However, the magnitude is also small (0.001 in SFA vs 0.035 in DEA percentage points). The negative influence of the increase in LFA payments on TE confirms our main hypothesis. Indeed, the added part of the LFA might generate a wealth effect (Hennesy, 1998; Sckokai and Moro, 2006), which in turn induces the relaxation of managerial effort (Zhu and Milán Demeter, 2012; Latruffe et al., 2009). Moreover, farms consider the LFA payments as a stable source of income (Hanus et al., 2017), which might accentuate the wealth effect.

5.3 How did farmers fare after the loss of the PHAE?

Table 6 provides insights on the loss of the PHAE. First, we observe a reduction in the share of grassland. The magnitude of the reduction is 0.035 percentage points, which is lower than the one found by Gallic and Marcus (2019). This result was somewhat expected and could be related to the conversion carried out by PHAE beneficiaries, as shown by Desjeux et al. (2015). Indeed, the loss of the PHAE could influence farms to convert permanent grassland to temporary grassland or crop land. This low magnitude gives credit to the suppression of the PHAE, as it does not translate to much loss in grassland.

Table 6: Comparison between *loser* and *neutral*

	Technical Efficiency		Environmental Efficiency	
	SFA	DEA	SFA	Eco-Efficiency
Average effect on treated	-0.008*	-0.023	0.002	-0.078
Standard error	(0.004)	(0.030)	(0.066)	(0.078)
	Specialization rate	Grassland rate	Loading rate	
Average effect on treated	0.733	-0.035	0.015	
Standard error	(1.276)	(0.029)	(0.059)	
Number of observations	3546	3546	3546	3546

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * $p < 0.10$ ** $p < 0.05$ *** $p < 0.01$. The estimations are made on a balanced panel. Propensity score is used as weight for the ATT.

The loss negatively affects the eco-efficiency of farms. However, the results are not sig-

nificant. Indeed, the loss implies a reduction of 0.078 percentage points in the capacity of farms to reduce environmental pressures while maintaining their value added. This reduction can be related to the increase in the dependence on fertilizers and pesticides. Indeed, grassland reduces dependence on these detrimental inputs, as underlined by [Bareille and Dupraz \(2020\)](#).

The study also found a significant reduction in TE, particularly when calculated using the stochastic frontier analysis (SFA) method. The loss of PHAE led to a decrease of 0.008 percentage points in farms' ability to increase their output using the same level of inputs. This decline in TE could be due to the reduction in the amount of subsidies received, which may have affected farms' capacity to achieve production goals. Previous research on the link between subsidies and technical efficiency has shown predominantly negative effects, as subsidies tend to allow farms to smooth production risks without adopting efficient production strategies ([Minviel and Latruffe, 2017](#)). Thus, losing a significant amount of subsidies (on average 4525 EUR) could cause financial stress and result in the loss of a source of income that was previously dedicated to investment in advanced technologies ([Zhu and Lansink, 2010](#)).

6 Discussion and concluding remarks

We evaluate both the loss of the grassland premium and the revaluation of the LFA payment following the 2015 CAP reform in France. This reform provides a valuable opportunity for a quasi-natural experiment, which we exploit using difference-in-difference with inverse propensity score weight. Specifically, we investigate its effects on grassland share as well as farm technical and environmental efficiency, measured through stochastic frontier analysis (SFA) and Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA).

Our research makes several contributions. Firstly, it is the first study that we are aware of that analyzes the impact of an increase of the LFA payment reform on technical efficiency with a natural experiment. Secondly, to the best of our knowledge, we are the first to evaluate the impact of PHAE and LFA payments on environmental efficiency. Thirdly, our study is only the second one that evaluates the 2015 LFA payment reform. Finally, we assess the impact of the loss of subsidies on technical and environmental efficiency in Europe.

The study findings reveal that farmers who lost the grassland premium experienced a decline in technical efficiency (TE), which could be attributed to the importance of the grassland premium in farm income. The *winners* group, who received an increase in LFA payments, also showed a reduction in TE. The reduction in TE for the *winners* group could be due to a wealth effect that could negatively impact managerial capacity. Regarding environmental outcomes, The non significant effect showed in our study were generally consistent with previous research ([Hennessy, 1998](#); [Latruffe et al., 2009](#); [Desjeux et al., 2015](#)).

In light of our findings, we conclude of an asymmetric effect of grassland conservation payments: whether increasing or decreasing, these payments hurt technical efficiency. Although our estimated ATT appear relatively modest (*e.g.* compared to [Latruffe et al., 2017](#)), they translate into financial losses that are significant enough for public authorities to be concerned about the impact of such a reform. A back-of-the-envelope calculation of the financial loss induced by the reform in our sample results in a loss of between 11400 and

14400 € for the loser group and between 12000 and 24000 € for the winner group. One interesting finding is the asymmetric effect of a quasi-experimental variation in public subsidies on the technical efficiency of farms. These results also called for a proper exit strategy in terms of agricultural subsidies program as a sudden reduction or elimination can affect farms resilience and financial capacities.

Furthermore, these changes have no statistically significant effect on environmental efficiency or the grassland share of the UAA. The combination of these results suggests that the economic consequences of modifying this type of subsidy must be carefully assessed, as such reforms introduce an asymmetric economic shock to farms without contributing to improved environmental efficiency.

Our results highlight the negative impact of subsidy reforms on technical efficiency without any significant improvement in environmental efficiency, which raises concerns about the economic resilience of farms faced with conservation policies. In this context, the asymmetry of economic shocks resulting from changes in subsidies highlights the need to take into account the capacity of sectors to absorb these shocks while maintaining their technical and financial performance. Concretely, it is necessary to reassess the resilience model applied to ecological transition policies: subsidy reforms should be designed not only to achieve environmental objectives, but also to strengthen the resilience of farms to the economic shocks that these changes entail. By favoring Safe and Just operating space approaches ([Rockström et al., 2023](#)), we believe that public disbursers could focus on supporting a more sustainable and just transition, aligned with the economic and technical realities of the farms concerned.

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7 Appendices

AppendixA Efficiency Density Before and After The Reform

This section encompasses all density figures for our efficiency estimators before and after the 2015 CAP reform.

Figure A1: Technical efficiency (TE) density before and after the reform. The left figure is for *winners* and the right is for *losers*. The horizontal lines represent the mean.

Figure A2: Environmental efficiency via SFA (EE) density before and after the reform. The left figure is for *winners* and the right is for *losers*. The horizontal lines represent the mean.

Figure A3: Eco-efficiency via DEA (Eco-Ef) density before and after the reform. The left figure is for *winners* and the right is for *losers*. The horizontal lines represent the mean.

Figure A4: Energy eco-efficiency via DEA density before and after the reform. The left figure is for *winners* and the right is for *losers*. The horizontal lines represent the mean.

AppendixB Parallel Trend Graphs

This section presents parallel trend graphs for our main indicators. This parallel trend are made on sample without matching.

Figure B5: Parallel trend for the Technical efficiency.

Figure B6: Parallel trend for the Environmental efficiency via SFA.

Figure B7: Parallel trend for the Eco-efficiency via DEA (Eco-Ef).

Figure B8: Parallel trend for the Grassland Share .

AppendixC Additional Descriptive Statistics

Table C1: Other outcome description

Outcome	Methodology
Specialization rate	This is computed as the sum of permanent grassland, temporary grassland, fodder and , divided by the total UAA
Grassland rate	It is the ratio of permanent grassland to total UAA
Loading rate	The number of animals divided by the total UAA

Table C2: Statistics for different groups on main indicators: balanced panel

Variable	Looser			Neutral			Winner		
	N	mean	sd	N	mean	sd	N	mean	sd
UAA	162	119.32	37.92	2,826	130.76	85.63	2,655	112.17	76.29
LFA	–	–	–	2,826	11,890.1	9,583.79	2,655	7,609.82	5,857.75
PHAE	162	4,243.3	2,536.17	2,827	4,807.22	3,775.16	–	–	–
Technical Efficiency	162	0.68	0.15	2,826	0.69	0.16	2,655	0.69	0.15
Environmental Efficiency	162	0.44	0.27	2,826	0.44	0.25	2,654	0.38	0.22
Specialization Rate (%)	162	90.6	80.6	2,826	92.42	8.34	2,655	69.83	25.97
Grassland Rate	162	0.72	0.28	2,826	0.58	0.33	2,655	0.34	0.28
Loading Rate	162	1.24	0.57	2,826	1.08	1.12	2,655	1.11	.94
Technical Efficiency (DEA)	162	0.75	0.23	2,826	0.54	0.2	2,655	0.62	0.2
Eco-efficiency	162	0.47	0.31	2,826	0.26	0.24	2,655	0.21	0.19

Table C3: Parallel trend estimation for the two comparison groups

<i>winners vs neutrals</i>							
	Technical Efficiency	Environmental Efficiency	Specialization Rate	Grassland Rate	Loading Rate	Technical Efficiency (DEA)	Eco-Efficiency
ATT 2011	-0.000 (0.000)	-0.002 (0.006)	-0.305 (0.327)	0.005 (0.007)	-0.062 (0.086)	0.046** (0.018)	-0.012 (0.017)
ATT 2012	-0.001 (0.001)	-0.006 (0.007)	-0.228 (0.436)	0.012 (0.014)	0.003 (0.093)	0.039** (0.019)	0.022 (0.016)
ATT 2013	-0.001 (0.001)	-0.006 (0.007)	-0.397 (0.577)	0.002 (0.016)	-0.021 (0.103)	0.033* (0.019)	0.004 (0.021)
ATT 2014	-0.001 (0.001)	-0.005 (0.007)	-1.002 (0.675)	-0.003 (0.020)	-0.025 (0.103)	0.001 (0.019)	-0.001 (0.016)
N	1970	1970	1970	1970	1970	1970	1970
<i>losers vs neutrals</i>							
	Technical Efficiency	Environmental Efficiency	Specialization Rate	Grassland Rate	Loading Rate	Technical Efficiency (DEA)	Eco-Efficiency
ATT 2011	-0.000 (0.001)	-0.008 (0.008)	0.789** (0.396)	0.020 (0.015)	-0.069** (0.034)	0.143*** (0.039)	0.146* (0.085)
ATT 2012	-0.001 (0.001)	-0.006 (0.005)	0.195 (0.390)	-0.000 (0.017)	-0.037 (0.045)	0.070 (0.063)	0.080 (0.087)
ATT 2013	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.011 (0.013)	0.192 (0.996)	-0.016 (0.018)	0.006 (0.057)	0.029 (0.062)	0.025 (0.050)
ATT 2014	-0.001 (0.003)	-0.002 (0.009)	0.610 (0.809)	0.002 (0.019)	0.034 (0.054)	0.074 (0.047)	0.092 (0.056)
N	1660	1660	1660	1660	1660	1660	1660

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses. * p<0.10 ** p<0.05 *** p<0.01.